

VIEWS OF RUSSIAN LINGUISTS ON THE NOUN AS A PART OF SPEECH IN THE PERSIAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *Studying and analyzing the lexical composition of literary works plays an important role in illuminating the linguistic processes characteristic of certain stages of language development. In linguistics, classifying words into categories and identifying their similarities and differences has attracted scholars' attention since ancient times. In particular, theoretical views and opinions of Russian Orientalist scholars are evident in studies on the lexical features, semantic classification, thematic grouping, and derivational models of nouns and adjectives in the Persian language. Specifically, research by T.D. Chkheidze, L.S. Peysikov, Y.A. Rubinchik, T.A. Chavchavadze, B. Yarzada, and others contains information on the characteristics of compound words. However, their classifications of compound words are not identical. Despite differences, there are also convergent views among these scholars.*

Keywords: *part of speech, linguistics, Persian language, noun, Russian linguistics, word.*

Introduction

It is important to suggest that Rubinchik and L. Peysikov, in their research, emphasize that affixation (word formation through suffixes and prefixes) is one of the most widespread methods of word formation in the Persian language. In particular, Y. Rubinchik, in his studies emphasize that affixation (word formation through suffixes and prefixes) is one of the most widespread methods of word formation in the Persian language. In particular, Y. Rubinchik, in his work *Essays on the Grammar of the Persian Language*, classifies compound nouns in Persian into two groups based on the semantic relationship between their components:

1. Conjunctive compound nouns
2. Determinative (i.e., attributive) compound nouns

Moreover, in his study dedicated to the grammatical characteristics of contemporary literary Persian, Rubinchik defines nouns as follows:

"Nouns, according to their semantic and grammatical features, are divided into lexical-grammatical classes and categories. They can be classified, first, into proper and common nouns; second, into animate and inanimate nouns; and third, into concrete, abstract, and material nouns."

This definition indicates that Rubinchik's views are in harmony with those of Iranian linguists. The Georgian scholar T.D. Chkheidze is considered one of the linguists who studied the phenomenon of word formation in Persian nouns in depth. In his research, compound nouns are divided into four groups:

1. Conjunctive compound nouns
2. Reduplicated compound nouns
3. Determinative compound nouns
4. Possessive compound nouns

Among researchers of modern Persian lexicon, L. Peysikov classified compound nouns into three groups:

1. Determinative compound nouns
2. Copulative compound nouns
3. Compound nouns of a syntactic type (i.e., compound nouns in the form of phrases)

In both classification systems, it is evident that the grouping of compound nouns takes into account the semantic and formal relationships between the components of the compound words. Differences are also noticeable in the terminology used. The first and second groups are considered conventional, while the third group includes compound words formed from phrases.

Besides that, NT.A. Chavchavadze analyzed compound words in the Persian language. In his study, based on historical data of Persian and the classification of compound words in Sanskrit, he proposed a new classification system for Persian compound words, carried out their detailed modeling, and highlighted the morphological features of compound words, while also identifying the role of semantic factors in the composition (formation) of compound words.

According to G. Goleva, nouns denoting human body parts play an active role in the composition of phraseological units in Persian. They serve a figurative and symbolic function within these units. Words such as *dast*, *del*, *sar*, *pā*, and *čēšm* are identified as the most productive nouns participating in phraseological constructions. In the research of some linguists, nouns are classified into two groups based on their morphemic structure. In particular, S. Yusuf divides nouns into simple and compound types. In his work, nouns formed through processes such as reduplication, pairing, transposition, and lexicalization are also interpreted as compound nouns.

Article by B. Yarzada is devoted to the study of the syntactic positions of adjectives in Persian sentences, analyzing their functional possibilities. The research also examines the subordination of adjectives to nouns, the presence of prepositional and postpositional elements, and semantic changes that occur in context. The author relies on the theoretical views of the Iranian Linguist R. Vafoi in semantically classifying adjectives. Definitely, compound words in Persian have an ancient history. In particular, according to the Russian Linguist O. Chunakova, the emergence of copulative constructions dates back to the Middle Iranian period. To illustrate this, in the work *The Book of the Works of Ardashir, Son of Papak* (6th century AD), such paired synonymous constructions occur nearly forty times.

For example:

- späh ud gund – “troops” (literally: “soldier” and “unit”)
- cer ud nibardag – “warlike, militant” (literally: “active,” “strong,” and “warlike”)
- mihr ud dosāram – “love” (literally: “friendship” and “love”)

The use of such traditional formulas, i.e., copulative constructions, is also observed in other works written in Pahlavi. Certainly, the noun category in Persian is considered one of the oldest and most fundamental lexical-morphological layers of the language. Its thorough and systematic study contributes not only to the development of linguistic theory but also to understanding the history, present state, and prospects of the Persian language. With its semantic richness, grammatical functionality, and morphological structure, the noun occupies a central place in the overall structure of Persian. Research shows that Persian nouns form a complex and rich system according to semantic and grammatical criteria.

From a morphological perspective, Persian nouns are formed using various affixes and are expressed in grammatical categories such as gender, number, possession, case, and the genitive (ezafe) construction. In particular, ezafe constructions are a unique grammatical phenomenon

specific to Persian, serving to express relations of possession and definiteness between nouns. This construction, as a syntactic unit rarely found in other languages, is of special scholarly interest to linguists.

Additionally, historical-linguistic analysis demonstrates the changes that the noun category underwent in Old Persian, Middle Persian, and Modern Persian periods. These changes are observed at the phonetic, morphological, and semantic levels, providing insights into the internal mechanisms of language development. In this respect, Persian nouns offer rich empirical material for comparative studies within the Iranian language family.

Conclusion

Thus, scholarly analyses of the Persian noun category indicate that nouns not only serve a naming function but also play an active role in the structural, semantic, and stylistic systems of the language. Their grammatical formation, morphological variability, syntactic connections expressed through the *ezafe* construction, word-formation potential, and historical development hold invaluable significance in the overall evolution of the Persian language. A comprehensive study of the noun category serves as a critical resource in addressing both theoretical and practical issues in Persian linguistics, particularly in grammatical typology, word-formation mechanisms, and translation studies.

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